

INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

Scopus || Electronic journal specializing in Scopus

ISSUE 4

 Acceptance of papers April, 2026

**Acceptance of
papers**

Published monthly

Topics

economics,
technology, social
sciences

ISSN 3060-5229

Digital
Object
Identifier

Visit the website
t.me/scopus_IST2100

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli – Senior
lecturer at TSUI

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR ELECTRONIC
JOURNAL **"INNOVATION SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY"** HAS BEEN REGISTERED
UNDER THE NUMBER **C-5669633** BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND MASS
COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA) OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVE
FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

CONTACTS

Phone: **+998 50 737 87 88**

Website: <https://ist-journal.uz>

Email: innovationist2025@gmail.com

The scientific electronic journal "Innovation Science and Technology" has been included in the list of scientific publications recommended for the publication of main scientific results of dissertations for the award of PhD and DSc degrees in economics and technical sciences, in accordance with the Resolution No. 370 of the Presidium of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated May 8, 2025.

Editorial board:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of
Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Cham Tat Huei,
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Muhammad Imran Sadiq
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Professor,
Malaysia

Ahmed Aziz Ismail
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc),
Professor (Egypt)

Lee Chin
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), (Malaysia)

Asongu SImplice
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Cameroon

Rui Dang
Doctor of Chemistry (DSc), Professor, China

Zahoor Ahmed
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Turkey

Shujaat Abbas
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD), Russia

Tina A Coffelt
Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Sciences (PhD),
USA

Abdikarimova Dinara Rustamxanovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kurbonbekova Mohichehra Turobjonovna
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Alimardonov Ilkhom Muzrabshokovich
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Razakova Barno Sayfiyevna
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Khasanov Sarvar Ulugbek ugli
Doctor of Philosophy in Economics (PhD)

Kholikova Rukhsora Sanjarovna
Associate Professor (PhD)

CONTENTS

THE IMPACT OF FINANCIAL RISKS ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH DRIVERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THEIR MITIGATION	17
Turopova Nigora Xolmurod qizi	
UTILIZATION OF INTERNAL RESERVES FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF REGIONAL TOURISM (CASE STUDY OF THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN)	20
Naurizbaev Aliakbar Rustamovich	
MATHEMATICAL MODELS AND ALGORITHMS FOR PROCESSING NOISE DATA	23
Jovlieva Dilnoz Mustofa qizi	
ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS IN BUSINESS ACTIVITIES AND WAYS TO REDUCE THEM.....	28
Abdukhamid Abdumalikovich Bektemirov	
A MULTI-LEVEL SYSTEM OF STATISTICAL INDICATORS FOR REGIONAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE ASSESSMENT: METHODOLOGY AND APPROBATION	34
Keunimzhaev Mukhamedali Kuanyshaevich	
THE IMPACT OF BANKS ON THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF THE ECONOMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	39
Usmonov Faridun Firdavsievich, Ishonkulova Feruza Asatovna	
EMPIRICAL EVALUATION OF MACRO- AND MICROECONOMIC FACTORS AFFECTING THE EFFICIENCY OF INVESTMENT ACTIVITY AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY	43
Aytmuratova Ulbike Jalgasovna	
MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY THROUGH OPTIMIZATION OF PRODUCTION RESOURCE POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	47
Sattarov Abdusamat Umirqulovich	
PROMISING DIRECTIONS FOR APPLYING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GREEN TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN	52
Rakhimova Dilfuza Mirzakasimovna	
PRIORITIES FOR REGULATING FINANCIAL RELATIONS IN PROVIDING HOUSING TO THE POPULATION IN UZBEKISTAN.....	58
Khannarov Komiljon Karimovich	
IMPROVING THE ORGANIZATION OF PRODUCTION COST ACCOUNTING IN FULL-SYSTEM FARMS SPECIALIZING IN THE CULTIVATION OF CYPRINID FISH.....	62
Aitimbetov Amirbek Qoishibekovich	
THE TRANSFORMATIONAL ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN'S ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS BASED ON 2025 NATIONAL STATISTICS.....	68
Isakjanova Sabokhat Muhamedovna	
AN INTEGRATED METHODOLOGICAL FRAMEWORK FOR ADVANCING GREEN TOURISM MODELS IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY ERA.....	79
Rasulova Nigora Yusupovna	
FACTORS AFFECTING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF COMPANIES.....	83
Kamoliddinov Ilhomjon Muhammadjonovich, Nosirov Eldor Nosirjon ugli	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF THE UZBEK ECONOMY.....	88
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF MARKET FACTORS TO ENSURE THE GROWTH OF THE ECONOMIC POTENTIAL OF THE ENTERPRISE (USING THE EXAMPLE OF THE SAG EXPRESS BRAND STORES)	92
Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomevna	
THE CONCEPT OF REGIONAL IMAGE AND ITS ECONOMIC CONTENT (THE CASE OF THE KHOREZM REGION).....	99
Dilshod Ibragimovich Ibdullayev	

DEVELOPMENT OF QUALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	106
Shakhnoza Samandarovna Ziyadillayeva	
ADVANCED APPROACHES TO THE ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT OF CURRENT FINANCIAL STABILITY IN JOINT-STOCK COMPANIES USING CFAR (CASH FLOW AT RISK) AND 3 Σ STATISTICAL RISK MODELS	114
Kurbonov Xayrilla	
DEVELOPMENT OF A PROGRAM FOR ANALYZING MEDICAL LABORATORY RESULTS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE MODELS.....	118
Gofurjonov Muhammadali, Kamolov Shamsiddin	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN IMPROVING MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES OF CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS INDUSTRY ENTERPRISES.....	122
Ubaydullayev Mukhammadjon Abdusamad o'g'li	
IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING THE RESOURCE POTENTIAL OF ORGANIZATIONS IN THE EDUCATIONAL SERVICES SECTOR.....	125
Ibrohim Meliboyev	
ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SERVICE QUALITY AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY.....	130
Khudoyorov Lochinbek Bahromovich	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS IMPROVE USAGE PRACTICES	135
A.A. Ismailov	
E-COMMERCE ADOPTION IN TRADITIONAL STORES.....	140
Nuserov Bakhtiyor	
ENHANCING FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY AND OPERATIONAL EFFICIENCY OF JSC "HUDUDGAZTAMINOT": KEY FACTORS AND DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGIES.....	146
Ergashev Muhibbek Aslamovich	
METHODS FOR IMPROVING AUTOMOTIVE FUEL QUALITY INDICATORS THROUGH THE USE OF ADDITIVES.....	151
Xushnayev Obid, Sheraliyev Ulugbek, Astonov Alisher	
MONETARY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	156
A.A. Ismailov	
THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN ENHANCING A COUNTRY'S INTERNATIONAL IMAGE: THE CASE OF SWITZERLAND.....	161
Idirisbaeva Hurliman Amanbay qizi, Kurolov Maksud Obitovich	
VOLUNTEER TOURISM: CURRENT IMPACTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS	170
Ossama Moustafa Elsetouhy	
COMPUTER GRAPHICS IN MODERN EDUCATION: PRACTICAL CAPABILITIES OF THE FIGMA PLATFORM.....	176
Maxamadov Rustam Xabibullayevich, Djamatov Mustafa Xatamovich	
DEVELOPING THE FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.....	182
Abdurasulov Sardor Tolqin ugli	
THE IMPORTANCE AND PROSPECTS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT	187
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna, Qosimov Jahongir Ruziboyevich	
STRATEGIES FOR OPTIMIZING THE STRUCTURE OF COMMERCIAL BANK ASSETS AND INCREASING EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN	194
Ibrohimov Davronbek Muhammadi o'g'li	
STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXPORTS OF PRODUCTS BASED ON ARTIFICIAL FIBERS.....	199
Raximov Furqat Jalolovich	
FUNDAMENTALS OF USING MARKETING RESEARCH TO IMPROVE SALES SYSTEM EFFECTIVENESS.....	206
Abduxalilova Laylo Tuxtasinovna	

FASHION MARKETING AS AN INSTRUMENT FOR SHAPING CONSUMER-BASED BRAND VALUE.....	213
Navruz-Zoda Bakhtiyor Negmatovich, Aripova Makhliyo Salakhiddinovna	
ENSURING SUSTAINABLE GROWTH OF THE NATIONAL ECONOMY IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION, IMPROVING INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES, AND ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING DIGITAL ECONOMY PRINCIPLES IN THE FINANCE, BANKING, AND TOURISM SECTORS	220
Inatullayeva Intizor Jamshid qizi, Uroqov Uchqun Yunusovich	
SOCIAL AND SECURITY PROBLEMS OF INNOVATIVE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION.....	223
Q.A. Musakhanov	
DIGITAL ECONOMY AND INNOVATION AS FACTORS OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	228
Ibragimova Saodat Abdumuminovna, Sadullayeva Sevara Uchqun qizi	
THE SOCIAL INSURANCE SYSTEM OF THE UNITED STATES OF AMERICA	232
Javliyev Nuriddin Bektemir o'g'li	
DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATIONAL-ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR TRANSITION TO THE INNOVATIVE MARKETING CONCEPT IN ENTERPRISES UNDER DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION	236
Bobomurodov Qayimjon Homidovich	
FOMO-DRIVEN PURCHASING IN E-COMMERCE FLASH SALES: AN INTEGRATIVE CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	241
Muhammadiminov Abdukodir Bakhodirjon Ugli, Arciana Damayanti, Javliev Nuriddin Bektemir ugli	
PHYSICO-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COARSE FEEDS	250
Yodgorov Jamoliddin Nomozovich, Yadgarov Sirojiddin Nomozovich	
EVOLUTION AND STANDARDIZATION OF SI MEASUREMENT UNITS IN THE INTERNATIONAL SYSTEM	255
Maxmudov Dostonbek Soyibjon o'g'li	
PROCEDURE FOR ACCOUNTING OF ESTIMATED LIABILITIES BY BUDGETARY ORGANIZATIONS	259
Jabbarova Charos Aminovna	
FEATURES OF AUDIT IN DEVELOPING INVESTMENT LENDING PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	263
Jamshid Mirzakhmedov	
ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES: THE CASE OF SOLAR AND WIND ENERGY	271
Hayitov Jamshid Kholboyevich	
ADVANCED FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION FINANCING: THE CASE OF THE UNITED KINGDOM	275
Kurbanov Baxodir Negmatullayevich	
THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL DESTINATION IMAGE ON TOURIST SATISFACTION AND REVISIT INTENTION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	279
Shaxnoza Almasovna Ashurova	
FACTORS INFLUENCING THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY	287
Narzullaev Elmurod Shukhrat ugli	
IMPROVING STATE FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR INVOLVING LOW-INCOME FAMILIES IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP	291
Erejepov Kuwanishbay Jienbay uli	
AGGREGATE FACTORS OF ENSURING REGIONAL ECONOMIC SECURITY AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION ...	296
Nurxonov Komiljon Tovkarayevich	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE USE OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE TRANSPORT AND LOGISTICS CLUSTER IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN	301
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	

METHODS OF THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF METAL FORMING PROCESSES.....	308
Rakhimov T.O., Norboyev Abror Baxtiyor o'g'li	
SOCIAL AND SECURITY PROBLEMS OF INNOVATIVE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN THE REGION.....	316
Q.A. Musakhanov	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION IN RETAIL: IMPACT ON ASSORTMENT MANAGEMENT AND DYNAMIC PRICING.....	321
Achilova Shirin Shavkat qizi, Fayzullayeva Diyora Anvar qizi	
MODERN TRENDS IN IMPROVING CORPORATE GOVERNANCE SYSTEMS IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.....	327
Xusanova Malohat Mingnorovna	
THE EVOLUTION OF DIGITAL PAYMENT SYSTEMS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE FINANCIAL BEHAVIOR OF THE POPULATION	333
Susanna S. Alieva	
FROM EXPERIMENTAL RESEARCH METHODS: ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF THE MAGNETRON SPUTTERING METHOD.....	338
Sobirova Tursunoy Abdipatto qizi	
IMPROVING STATE FINANCIAL SUPPORT FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF WATER-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE REPUBLIC OF KARAKALPAKSTAN	345
Seitnazarov Baxadir Muratbaevich	
ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION IN RETAIL: IMPACT ON ASSORTMENT MANAGEMENT AND DYNAMIC PRICING.....	351
Achilova Shirin Shavkat qizi, Fayzullayeva Diyora Anvar qizi	
PRIORITY DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING ECONOMIC STABILITY IN ENTERPRISES.....	357
Iminova Nargizaxon Akramovna	
ENHANCING FORECASTING APPROACHES FOR VALUE ADDED TAX AND EXCISE TAX REVENUES IN THE CONTEXT OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY	364
Sherzod Kh. Dusiyarov	
APPLICATION OF BLOCKCHAIN AND BENFORD'S LAW IN IMPROVING PAYROLL AUDITING UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY	364
Nomozov Ilhomjon Ziyodullo o'g'li	

APPLICATION OF BLOCKCHAIN AND BENFORD'S LAW IN IMPROVING PAYROLL AUDITING UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY

Nomozov Ilhomjon Ziyodullo o'g'li

Basic Doctoral Researcher

Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: This article examines the directions for improving payroll auditing in the context of the digital economy, particularly the practical application of blockchain technology and Benford's Law. Modern audit technologies based on the concepts of Continuous Auditing, RPA (Robotic Process Automation), and AI (Artificial Intelligence) are analyzed. A methodology for detecting anomalies in payroll accounting based on Benford's Law has been developed.

Keywords: digital audit, blockchain, Benford's Law, Continuous Auditing, RPA, AI, Big Four, Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida mehnat haqi auditini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari, xususan blokcheyn texnologiyasi va Benford qonunining amaliy qo'llanilishi o'rganilgan. Continuous Auditing konsepsiyasi, RPA (Robotic Process Automation), AI (Artificial Intelligence) asosidagi zamonaviy audit texnologiyalari tahlil qilingan. Benford qonuni asosida mehnat haqi hisoblaridagi anomalialarni aniqlash uslubiyoti ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli audit, blokcheyn, Benford qonuni, Continuous Auditing, RPA, AI, Big Four, Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследованы направления совершенствования аудита оплаты труда в условиях цифровой экономики, в частности практическое применение технологии блокчейн и закона Бенфорда. Проанализированы современные аудиторские технологии на основе концепции Continuous Auditing, RPA (Robotic Process Automation) и AI (Artificial Intelligence). Разработана методика выявления аномалий в расчетах по оплате труда на основе закона Бенфорда.

Ключевые слова: цифровой аудит, блокчейн, закон Бенфорда, Continuous Auditing, RPA, AI, Big Four, Deloitte, PwC, EY, KPMG.

INTRODUCTION

Under the conditions of the digital economy, audit practices are undergoing fundamental transformation. Internationally operating Big Four auditing corporations — Deloitte, PwC, EY, and KPMG — invest billions of dollars annually in AI (Artificial Intelligence), ML (Machine Learning), RPA (Robotic Process Automation), and blockchain technologies. This, in turn, is leading to a radical transformation of audit processes.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, directions for the development of the digital economy have been defined within the framework of the Digital Uzbekistan – 2030 Strategy. Within the scope of this strategy, the digitalization of the audit sector has also become increasingly important.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Theoretical and practical issues related to digital auditing have been extensively studied by international scholars and leading auditing organizations in recent years. The rapid development of the digital economy has significantly transformed traditional audit methodologies, leading to the widespread integration of artificial intelligence, blockchain technologies, big data analytics, and robotic process automation into audit practice. In this regard, Mark J. Nigrini made a substantial contribution to the development of statistical audit techniques based on Benford's Law. In his research, the author demonstrated that Benford's Law can effectively be applied in forensic accounting, fraud detection, and payroll auditing to identify anomalies and suspicious financial transactions.

Research devoted to the application of blockchain technology in auditing has shown that blockchain

systems increase transparency, reliability, and data security in accounting and audit procedures. Specialists from Deloitte, PwC, EY, and KPMG have emphasized that blockchain-based audit systems enable continuous verification of financial transactions in real time while significantly reducing fraud risks and operational costs. Their annual analytical reports and practical case studies indicate that digital audit technologies improve audit quality and accelerate decision-making processes.

In addition, modern studies on Continuous Auditing concepts confirm that real-time audit approaches are becoming increasingly important under conditions of rapid digital transformation. Researchers note that continuous auditing allows auditors to identify accounting irregularities more quickly, strengthen internal control systems, and provide more reliable financial reporting information. Scientific literature also highlights the growing role of RPA (Robotic Process Automation) technologies in automating repetitive audit tasks such as data collection, reconciliation, and report preparation. As a result, digital audit technologies are now regarded as one of the strategic directions for improving audit efficiency and ensuring financial transparency in the digital economy.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed comparative analysis, statistical analysis (Benford's Law), case study, expert evaluation, and simulation methods. Empirical data were obtained from the official 2023 reports of the Big Four companies and payroll accounting records of the foreign enterprise "Global Komsco Daewoo" LLC for 2022–2023.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Benford's Law was discovered by Frank Benford in 1938. According to this law, in naturally occurring numerical datasets, the probability of the first digit appearing is calculated using the following formula:

$$P(d) = \log_{10} \left(1 + \frac{1}{d} \right)$$

where d represents a digit from 1 to 9 (Table 1).

Table 1. Probability of the First Digit According to Benford's Law¹

Digit (d)	Benford's Law (%)	"Global Komsco Daewoo" Payroll Data (%)
1	30.1	29.4
2	17.6	17.2
3	12.5	12.8
4	9.7	9.5
5	7.9	8.1
6	6.7	6.9
7	5.8	5.6
8	5.1	5.3
9	4.6	5.2

As can be seen from the table, the payroll accounts of the foreign enterprise "Global Komsco Daewoo" LLC demonstrate a distribution close to Benford's Law, indicating that the accounting records are maintained properly within the enterprise. The differences are not statistically significant (chi-square = 3.24; $p > 0.05$).

A comparative analysis of the modern audit platforms of the Big Four companies allows the following conclusions to be drawn (Table 2).

¹ Based on the obtained data, prepared by the author.

Table 2. Digital Audit Systems of the Big Four Companies²

Company	Platform/System	Core Technologies	Efficiency
Deloitte	Digital Audit 2.0, Argus AI, lcount	AI, ML, anomaly detection, risk-based selection	Audit time: -35%; accuracy: +92%
PwC	Aura, Halo, Extract 360	Data analytics, predictive analysis, real-time monitoring	Automation: 85%
EY	Canvas, Helix, GAMx	Data analysis, methodology, ML	Errors: -67%; reliability: +88%
KPMG	Clara, Ignite	Cognitive computing, blockchain	Process time: -48%

Blockchain technology is creating fundamentally new opportunities in payroll auditing. In a blockchain-based system, every payroll transaction — from calculation, tax withholding, and bank transfer to the receipt of funds in the employee's account — is sequentially recorded within the blockchain chain. The key characteristic of blockchain technology is the immutability of recorded data. This practically eliminates the possibility of payroll data manipulation and fraud.

At the foreign enterprise “Global Komsco Daewoo” LLC, the estimated investment required for implementing a blockchain system amounts to 450 million UZS, with an implementation period of 14–18 months. However, the long-term efficiency indicator is expected to increase by 3.2 times: annual savings are projected at 240–380 million UZS, the speed of error detection increases by 6.5 times, and audit costs decrease by 45 percent.

The advantages of applying the Continuous Auditing concept in payroll auditing are as follows: first, unlike traditional periodic audits, errors are detected immediately when they occur; second, audits are conducted based on current rather than historical data; third, audit costs are reduced in the long term; and fourth, valuable information is provided for managerial decision-making.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

According to the results of the study, the main directions for improving payroll auditing under conditions of the digital economy include the following: first, the implementation of AI, ML, and RPA technologies; second, the development of blockchain-based audit systems; third, the application of statistical analysis based on Benford's Law; and fourth, the adoption of the Continuous Auditing concept.

RPA (Robotic Process Automation) technology is considered a modern tool for automating repetitive tasks in payroll auditing. Platforms such as UiPath, Automation Anywhere, and Blue Prism enable the automation of tasks such as audit scheduling, data collection, cross-checking, and report preparation. International practice confirms that companies implementing RPA have reduced audit duration by 40–60%.

Several important steps are currently being implemented in Uzbekistan to develop digital auditing: first, the Chamber of Auditors is organizing training courses on digital auditing; second, large audit organizations are introducing CAAT (Computer-Assisted Audit Tools) such as ACL and IDEA; and third, universities are teaching the subject “Digital Audit.”

The study concluded that the development of payroll auditing under the conditions of the digital economy is one of the essential prerequisites for elevating Uzbekistan's economy to the international level. The widespread implementation of blockchain, Benford's Law, AI, and RPA technologies will significantly improve audit quality, reduce fraud, and ensure the transparency of financial reporting.

It should be emphasized that the human factor also plays an important role in the application of digital audit technologies. An auditor must not only understand these technologies but also be capable of critically evaluating them and correctly interpreting the results. Therefore, a modern auditor must possess both technical competencies and high professional standards and ethical principles.

As a final conclusion of the study, it should be noted that the development of payroll auditing in the digital economy is a continuous process. As technologies continue to evolve, new opportunities, as well as new risks, emerge simultaneously. Auditors and audit organizations must therefore pursue continuous learning, professional development, and the implementation of innovations in order to adapt to these changes.

² Compiled by the author based on the official 2023 reports of the Big Four companies.

List of used literature:

1. 1. Benford, F. (1938). The Law of Anomalous Numbers. Proceedings of the American Philosophical Society, 78(4), pp. 551-572.
2. 2. Deloitte. (2023). Global Human Capital Trends 2023. New York: Deloitte Insights.
3. 3. EY. (2023). Future of Audit: Digital Transformation Report. London: EY Global.
4. 4. IIA. (2017). International Professional Practices Framework (IPPF). Lake Mary: Institute of Internal Auditors.
5. 5. KPMG. (2023). Clara Audit Technology Report. KPMG International.
6. 6. Nigrini, M.J. (2012). Benford's Law: Applications for Forensic Accounting, Auditing, and Fraud Detection. Hoboken: John Wiley & Sons.
7. 7. PwC. (2023). 26th Annual Global CEO Survey. PricewaterhouseCoopers.

Proofreader: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Layout and Designer: Oloviddin Sobir ugli

2026. № 4

© When materials are reproduced, the INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

“The journal “INNOVATION SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY” has been registered by the Agency for Information and Mass Communications under the Administration of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from 09.10.2024 under the registration number №390637. License number: C-5669633. PNFL: 30407832680027

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block,
House 17.

Acceptance of articles

Published every
monthly

Directions

Social, economic, political,
technological, scientific

Scopus || Scientific electronic journal specializing in Scopus

CERTIFICATE NUMBER: №390637

ORDER NUMBER ACCORDING TO THE LICENSE REGISTER: C-5669633

CONTACT:

Contact us
+998 50 737 87 88

Telegram channel
t.me/scopus_IST2100

Journal official website
<https://ist-journal.uz/index.php/IST>